

THE DEVELOPMENT MODEL OF LEARNING COMPETENCY OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article talks about the systematic preparation of future physics teachers for methodological activities and the competencies that a modern teacher must master. The content of the model for the development of educational competence of future physics teachers through an educational physics experiment is also revealed.*

Keywords: *future teacher, competence, experiment, educational competence, consistency, communication, constructiveness, quality of education, model, target block, conceptual block, process block, result block.*

INTRODUCTION. Pedagogical activity of future teachers is aimed at forming a human personality. Each student has his own behavior and character, and it is a difficult process to take these features into account and learn them in education. Pedagogical activity is creative in nature. It is known that creativity is needed only when a person faces a problem. Teaching activity is related to the main essence of pedagogical creativity, the purpose and character of pedagogical activity. Pedagogical activity is the process of solving innumerable pedagogical issues subordinated to the common goal of forming a person's personality, worldview, beliefs, consciousness, and behavior.

RESEARCH MATERIALS. Creativity in the teacher's activity is expressed in the methods of solving these problems, in their ability to find ways to solve them. The source of pedagogical creativity is pedagogical experience. By advanced pedagogical experience, we understand the teacher's creative approach to his pedagogical task, searching for new, effective ways and means of student education [3].

In order to effectively organize education, a modern teacher should have the following competencies: a) to have deep and thorough knowledge of the subject he teaches, to constantly research on himself; b) organizing the educational process using pedagogical and innovative technologies while ensuring the content integrity of lectures, practical and laboratory sessions; c) designing a pedagogical system in accordance with the content of teaching subjects; d) taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, demonstrating their skills, knowledge and competence; e) taking into account the interests, abilities and requirements of students, creating conditions for them to acquire knowledge thoroughly; f) ensuring interrelationship of academic subjects studied by students; g) activation of a person's all-round development based on the unity and interdependence of education and upbringing.

Research activity of future teachers includes the following: performing tasks related to information search, conducting analytical research; performing abstract reviews of scientific literature, conducting research within the scientific work of teachers. These forms of work are aimed at developing students' basic research abilities and skills (working with primary sources; searching, analyzing and systematizing the obtained data; processing experimental data using mathematical statistical methods; using information technologies, etc.).

Figure 1. Types of activities of future physics teachers reflecting systematicity

The goal of students' research activities outside of class is to expand the content of professional training provided in curricula and programs. The variability of such activities allows teachers to use a wide range of forms, including internships of future teachers at other universities and research organizations; the work of students in research groups for the implementation of projects, etc. [4].

Figure 2. Systematic training of future physics teachers for methodical activity

Academic knowledge: every physics teacher must have in-depth theoretical knowledge of his subject, participate in the promotion and popularization of science through scientific and technical achievements. The main internal motivation for a person's professional activity is to know the world around him, the task of the teacher is to support and develop this motive in the student, to bring it to the level of need.

The communicative competence of future teachers is reflected in the process of communication with a group of students or an individual student, parents, colleagues working together in the team, and management. Future teachers acquire communicative experience not only in the process of direct interactions, but also from literature, theater, cinema, radio, and various television programs (round talks, etc.). He also receives information about the nature of communicative situations, problems of interpersonal relations and how to solve them, analyzes them, summarizes them, and draws conclusions. As a result, he forms in his mind the knowledge, skills and competences that ensure effective communication with others. Communicative competence implies the flexibility of verbal and other non-verbal means of communication and the freedom to use them. It can be considered as a category that regulates the system of relations of a person to himself, to the natural and social world [9].

The following three stages are important in the teacher's preparation for the lesson in his subject: diagnosis, prediction, design (planning). During diagnosis, the teacher specifies all the

conditions under which the didactic process takes place, determines its results. Forecasting is the teacher's consideration and evaluation of various options for the effective organization of the future lesson, selecting and applying the most appropriate option according to the accepted criteria. Designing (planning) is the creation of a program for managing students' educational activities, which is the final stage of preparing for the lesson.

Modeling - "the method of researching objects of knowledge in their models; to define or improve descriptions of clearly existing objects, events and constructive objects, to facilitate and control their creation methods, etc. Modeling is a method that simplifies every object of science. Therefore, the model solves the problem that traditional theories could not explain, discovers a side of the object that was not observed before, but may be realized in the future [6].

Constructive competencies of future physics teachers are manifested in their organization of laboratory and demonstration experiments in physics and in the formation of devices, in assembling various electric circuits, in conducting technical-constructive circles in extracurricular activities, etc. Special attention should be paid to the application of fundamental knowledge in the development of new technology in the formation of students' constructive competences. Such an approach arouses their interest in acquiring physical knowledge, therefore, it allows them to connect their professional activities with modern technologies in science and production in the future.

The technical-constructive competencies of a physics teacher should include three components:

- 1) mastering the content of the generalized method of solving technical and constructive issues;
- 2) learning to use this method in any specific situations;
- 3) to master the methodology of organizing cognitive activities of students to solve problems based on physical knowledge in the creation of new objects and technologies of practical importance.

The formation of the technical-constructive competences of the physics teacher is carried out by studying a number of educational subjects. In particular, in compulsory subjects such as general physics, physics teaching methodology, a seminar on school physics experiments, as well as in the process of studying elective subjects such as vocational training, the basics of robotics, electrical engineering and electronics, as well as physics lessons in the organization of outside circles.

Organization and management of the pedagogical process - the ability to organize a team of students, to unite the team, to properly organize the activities of the pedagogue. The teacher's organizational ability is manifested in the following: proper organization of the pedagogue's activities; effective management of the student body; ability to solidify the team; successful management of students' educational activities; students' ability to master scientific knowledge, to be able to form their skills; correct and rational allocation of time during the lesson and effective and complete implementation of the plan; consistent organization of individual work with students; to conduct collective or group work with the group team on an ongoing basis; accustoming students to strict compliance with the internal procedures of the educational institution; giving students educational and social assignments taking into account their age, psychological and personal characteristics; successful management of students' attention; organizing a heated debate among students, managing it effectively; use of technology in lessons, achieving equal active participation

of all students; effectively increasing the educational activities of students, ensuring their independence; developing a list of educational tasks in cooperation with students [5].

The quality of education is a set of characteristics of the educational process that determines the consistent and practically effective formation of competence and professional consciousness. Three groups of characteristics can be distinguished here: the quality of the potential to achieve the educational goal, the quality of the process of professional formation, and the quality of the educational result.

Fundamentally improving the quality of education in physics, training highly qualified pedagogues and scientific staff, providing educational institutions with modern laboratories, textbooks and other educational equipment, developing the potential of scientific organizations, effectively organizing their activities, Establishment of close communication and cooperation between the fields of science and production is the demand of the time. The ongoing modernization of education in our country requires the solution of several tasks that have a negative impact on the quality of personnel training and the effectiveness of research [1].

The factors of education quality formation can be conditionally divided into two groups - external and internal.

External: state management of education (activities of the ministry), organizational and legal provision of education (Law on Education, State Education Standards, etc.), education financing system, includes manifestation of educational needs and public opinion about education, quality of education.

Internal: includes the composition of teachers and students, material and technical support of the educational process, information and methodological support, educational technology and educational work. A specialized quality management system (if any) and an educational program play a special role.

In all modern developments of the quality of education, the main focus is on achieving a certain level of it. But in the process of social development, the needs and conditions of education change, and then the requirements for quality and the criteria for its evaluation should change [7].

RESEARCH RESULTS. Based on the analysis of the results of the above-mentioned scientific researches and the results of our researches, a model of the development of learning-cognitive competence of future physics teachers by means of educational experiments was developed.

The qualification requirements for the training system of future physics teachers are the state educational standard of the field of pedagogy, the qualification requirements for the education direction of physics and astronomy, the National curriculum of general secondary education. determined based on Our model includes 4 blocks: goal, conceptual, process and result blocks. This model was chosen taking into account the specific characteristics of developing skills and competencies. The model of development of educational experimental competence of future physics teachers through educational experiments organizes pedagogical tools, establishes various connections between them, determines the order of their use, and takes into account the dynamics and integrity of development. This model: reflects the systematic composition of process elements; determines the nature of the relationship between system elements; systematizes the functions performed by the elements and the whole model.

The goal block reflects the use of educational experiments in the improvement of the methodology of developing the teaching-knowledge competence of future physics teachers by

means of educational experiments based on the social need of training physics teachers who meet the requirements of SES and qualifications. Also, this block will teach future teachers' personal qualities such as curiosity, diligence, discipline, initiative, independence, self-management, and professional qualities such as academics, communication, design, organization and evaluation of education

The conceptual block consists of goal-oriented, informative, active, experiential, competence, and systematic approaches, which are the methodological bases for the development of learning competence in future physics teachers. Also, the principles of fundamentality, universality, integrative, variability, practical orientation of pedagogical education, succession, scientific, demonstrability, convenience, accuracy, independence, individualization of the educational process are embedded in the content of education. The process of development of educational competence in future physics teachers is divided into intellectual, practical-operational, technological and creative stages.

Process block - the content of the organization of the educational process in the development of learning competence in future physics teachers (SES, qualification requirements, curriculum, science programs, educational methodological complex), used in the educational process methods (observation, problem-based teaching, design, analysis of concepts, brainstorming, starry sky, insert methods, creating tables and graphs, questions and answers), forms of educational organization (training in the auditorium and outside the auditorium, collective, including group, individual, independent learning) and tools (study guide, virtual laboratory and demonstration experiments, physical tools and equipment, charts and graphs, assignments, animations, video lessons).

The final block includes evaluation based on criteria and indicators for determining the development of professional and educational experimental competence in future teachers. In the process of training a future physics teacher, it is important to monitor and record the development of educational experimental competencies in students. Individual changes in each student should be monitored in time. Indicators of development of academic competence have a number of unique qualities. These indicators are often not taken into account in the educational process. Without taking these indicators into account, it is impossible to assess the future teacher's educational competence and readiness for scientific-pedagogical, scientific-research activities.

DISCUSSION. The content and result of the practical activity of the student who performs the assignment at the experimental level will have certain differences compared to conducting educational research at the theoretical level. This is determined by the methodology of scientific research. As a result, research at different levels will be different. The methodology of science determines the theoretical and empirical levels for conducting research. Empirical and theoretical competencies of conducting scientific research must be included in the training system of future physics teachers. They determine the future teacher's readiness and ability to engage in scientific-pedagogical or educational research in the future. It is possible to achieve positive results in the process of developing the educational competence of future physics teachers when education based on the close connection of theory and experiment is organized effectively [2].

Development of educational and cognitive competencies in students is carried out by performing physical experiments. In studying the subject of physics, it is necessary to use empirical level activities based on physical experiments, and it is also effective in some ways. Introducing the algorithm of scientific experiments into the process of conducting educational

experiments in higher education organizations helps students to develop their skills in scientific research. It is known that research skills are a component of research competencies [10].

Currently, the lack of motivation of school graduates and applicants to master physics, the public's insufficient assessment of the importance of physics education, the excessive complexity of the curricula of general secondary education, vocational schools, the interests and needs of students level is related to the lack of modern educational programs and methodological materials. The requirements of future specialists for physical knowledge and methods are not sufficiently taken into account. Therefore, it is necessary to use all the possibilities to ensure that physics education becomes an attractive field of knowledge and activity, to turn learning into a process of conscious motivation.

It should be noted that in the modern system of integration of natural sciences, the scale of physical scientific research is from microscopic (molecules, atoms, elementary particles, quarks, etc.) objects to very large macroscopic (Sun, stars, galaxies, etc.) objects. is expanding. At the same time, physics education is forming a modern scientific outlook, the methodology of solving interdisciplinary problems, the ability to comprehensively analyze processes and predict their development. The internal logic of the development of physics education is designed to integrate existing interdisciplinary sciences and technologies into a single and new stage landscape of natural science. This helps to implement the principle of socio-cultural compatibility in physics education as one of the most important aspects at the moment.

CONCLUSION. The main indicators of the development of educational competence are mastering the methods of scientific knowledge, using certain methods of mental activity (analysis, synthesis, generalization, abstraction, etc.), applying the knowledge and methods obtained depending on the proposed educational task. includes application. Taking into account and implementing all of the above are the main tasks in preparing a future teacher for pedagogical and research activities.

In the context of the development of educational competence, the study of physics issues within the framework of didactic principles such as fundamentality, scientificity and existence is becoming a particularly important factor today. These principles reflect the undoubted relevance of physics education, which reflects important aspects of the methodology of modern scientific activity. This creates the necessary conditions for new practical knowledge that directly affects intellectual development. The student himself is formed as a subject of knowledge and a creative person. Consequently, the organization of the study of modern physics issues within the framework of fundamental principles will have the character of innovative development. The presence of scientific content helps to consciously perceive the studied problems, encourages the student to work independently.

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